

CODING SHEET FOR TWITTER

Analyze items in chronological order.

- ✓ Words in **bold** are the labels of standardized values, use with that exact spelling
- ✓ Fields with the sign |__| are for numbers
- ✓ In fields (____) for lists of words or sentences copied from the text, as in qualifications, verbal reactions, symbols etc., use a slash (/) to demarcate pieces of non-contiguous text. Don't use inverted commas (") if they don't appear in the original
- ✓ In fields (____) where you use your own words, try to be concise.

GENERAL INFORMATION

1. Identification number: (leave as in downloaded database)
2. Date and Time: (leave as in downloaded database)
3. Citations (@): (leave as in downloaded database)
4. N. of retweets: (leave as in downloaded database)
5. N. of Favorite: (leave as in downloaded database)
6. N. of followers: (leave as in downloaded database)
7. Username: (leave as in downloaded database)
8. User's settlement (for public figures, google to retrieve info if not evident; for everyday people, only if self-attributed)
 - Autochthonous** or 1.5 generation
 - migrant** or asylum seeker, refugee etc.
 - settled** in the country already (first generation, if second, choose autochthonous)
 - foreign non-immigrant person**
 - mix of the former categories** [possible when more than one author]
 - unclear**
9. User's racialization (for public figures, google to retrieve info if not evident; for everyday people, only if self-attributed)
 - white** including migrants historically non-racialized as people of colour, e.g. Eastern Europeans
 - non-white**
 - both** [possible when more than one author]
 - unclear**
10. User's gender (for public figures, google to retrieve info if not evident; for everyday people, only if evident or self-attributed)
 - man**
 - woman**
 - non-binary**
 - various** [possible when more than one author]
 - unclear**

HEADERS AND TEXT

11. Hashtags (leave as in downloaded database)
12. Text: (leave as in downloaded database)

NARRATIVES AND FRAMES

13. Target narrative (the narrative, statement or episode on which the Twitter user commented. Write a tentative one and then recode in 5-10 categories in a dialogue, if possible, with narratives recoded for traditional media. In case there is no target narrative, write **N/A.**): _____
14. User's comment (the comment on the narrative, statement or episode reported in the previous field. Write a tentative one and then recode in 5-15 categories. In case there is no comment, write **N/A.**):

15. Frame (if possible, use frames recoded for traditional media and maybe add others or, if necessary, recode from scratch): _____

QUOTATION OR LINK

16. Reported or linked speech/text (also for indirect reported speech. Consider the most prominent).
 - 16.a [Use only for what is not already reported as text in the field of var. 12, e.g. for the content of a link, a meme or a screenshot] Content: copy the text (if meme or screenshot), the headline (if news) or summarize content in a sentence: _____
 - 16.b Voice
 - individual(s)** (ordinary person, non-institutional, non-political)
 - public official** (non-political)
 - politician** _____ (specify also the party)
 - NGO** or civil society association
 - activist** (social movements)
 - company** or professional organization
 - expert**
 - influencer**
 - clergy**
 - other media outlet**
 - 16.c Voice's settlement (for public figures, google to retrieve info if not evident; for everyday people, only if self-attributed)
 - autochthonous**
 - foreign non-immigrant person**
 - migrant** or asylum seeker, refugee etc.
 - settled** in the country already (first generation, if second, choose autochthonous)
 - mix of the former categories**
 - unclear**
 - 16.d Voice's racialization (for public figures, google to retrieve info if not evident; for everyday people, only if self-attributed)
 - white** including migrants historically non-racialized as people of colour, e.g. Eastern Europeans
 - non-white**
 - both**

16.e Voice's gender (for public figures, google to retrieve info if not evident; for everyday people, only if evident or self-attributed)

man

woman

non-binary

various

unclear or impossible to determine

16.f Via which medium [more than one is possible]

same platform

media outlet (which) _____

press release or conference

talk show (which) _____

other social media (which) _____

blog (which) _____

public or confidential document

unknown

OTHER ORIENTATION DEVICES

17. Non-discursive semiotic material (consider the first material only):

17a. Type of material

image

video

document (also for screenshots)

meme or vignette

17.b Describe the subject, specifying characters, setting and agency if useful: _____

17.c Source

same platform

other social media (which) _____

media outlet (which) _____

state body (which) _____

NGO or international organization _____

blog (which) _____

owner

unknown

17.d Annotations: write about significant material's features concerning likely effects on viewers etc.
